

Cyber Casing: Challenges and Taxonomy to Address the Problems in Cloud System through GMSP

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Abstract- In general Engineering science is involved in all quarters of the society and it has been evolving very much faster in the networking environments with some objectives to be fulfilled. This eventual evolvement has thrown some tasks in the distributed environments which have become cumbersome job to be accomplished by the network users. Data stored under such networks are very much difficult to get retrieved and it has become one of the most major tasks to get accomplished.

In the distributed networks like cloud computing environment, vulnerability from outside the networking environment is most happening issue. It will demand the users who are outside of the networking environment to show up their mettle to handle various attacks on the network. If they ignore this, and this may lead to cybercrimes over the network. Cyber casing is one of the technologies where it deals with the aspect of cybercrimes on various platforms such as social groups, etc. The concept of cyber casing plays a vital role in providing a solution for cybercrimes. This has become a great need to provide privacy to avoid or minimize the treats form external environments or users. The aspect of cyber casing of the object is a congruence of the parameter list of a particular object which will minimize the attacks on the network by implementing certain mechanisms in the networks like cloud computing.

A cyber cased object (Geo tagged) will possess certain data which may be vulnerable to external attacks. This will happen while transferring data and invoking the data of the cyber cased object over the network. The tasks like availability, reliability of the cyber cased object have become more critical in defining the performance of the cloud system. In this paper a framework “Geo tagged Message Session Protocol” (GMSP) has been proposed which really handle these tasks or issues effectively.

This framework protocol will provide at most privacy of the data so that availability and reliability of the objects greatly improved. The protocol will implement a router “The Onion Router” (TOR) in the distributed systems like Cloud Storage. This router has been improved to solve the tasks of cyber cased objects in cloud systems. This implements GMSP by addressing the required nodes through public key cryptography with IPsec. It improves performance of the object in platforms like Flickr, Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, etc.

This framework may use different public API’s programmatically so that the performance of the network is enhanced to increase of availability and reliability of such objects.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber casing has become very much predominant in social networking and real time systems. It has got a wide variety of social and legal problems in the world we live in. There is a positive association when objects are cyber cased and they are very much minimal. While implementing or using social groups, handling cyber cased objects have become very tough. In this context cyber security for cyber cased objects has become very much important to resolve certain security issues. While providing cyber security there are lots of issues and challenges, encounter within the networking groups and sometimes cybercrimes may happen across the networks. Cyber cased objects may not be available in time for retrieval and processing them. So it has become mandatory for those cyber cased objects to be under cyber privacy. When an object is cyber cased the geographical identification with respect to metadata such as Geo tagged photographs or videos or websites or posts will become cumbersome job to handle for the users in the network. This data is usually consists of latitude and longitude parameters of cyber cased objects. Sometimes geotagging can help the user in identifying the specific location with particular information for cyber cased objects. For instance a user can find images taken from a given location by giving latitude and longitude as parameters. A number of suitable image search engines are implemented such that the search engines will have a follow through and provide the user a location from where a cyber cased object can be retrieved. But this entire process happens above the system and is very much difficult for social networking groups for handling the cyber cased objects at this level. Dealing with such issues like availability and reliability of cyber cased objects is a cumbersome task in networks. During the cybercrimes, when objects are cyber cased, then they have been handled effectively through TOR router. This has been effectively implemented by introducing time frames in the networking domain. Resolving the cybercrime challenges will resolve the issues of reliability and availability of cyber cased objects. This will improve the performance of the system. A protocol GMSP has been introduced in this paper to handle such issues during the cybercrime and thereby the availability and reliability of cyber cased objects have been improved. This protocol will work at the granular level of the node in the network. This protocol has been implemented with public key and IPsec at the node level. The router will enable this public key mechanism to help of protocol suits.

II. CYBER CASING AND CHALLENGES

To handle the challenges like awareness of the system, training the manpower, policies related to geotagged objects, security attacks, failure results, maintaining standard protocols is a cumbersome job in a given social networking group. This is because of networks' vulnerability during the exchange of data. Sometimes this will lead to different cybercrimes in the distributed network. This may cause in the overall throughput in networking in the context of privacy and security. The networking users have faced too many problems in handling the challenges mentioned above. Global Positioning System (GPS) will aid the user in capturing photographs or images. These images sometimes may be cyber cased in networking groups based on parameters like position, interspace, location, radius, distance, timeframe, etc. These cyber cased entities are tagged with latitude and longitudinal positional parameters in the context of spatial data are concerned. The availability of cyber cased objects can be considered as an important issue in handling them. In this regard decreasing the Denial of service (DoS) will overcome the issue of

availability of a cyber cased object across the network. In this regard the objects facilitate the maximum information regarding accessibility as far as the objects are concerned.

The Onion Router (TOR) shown in Fig 1 will prevail lot of privacy issues while transferring information from one node to another. The cyber cased object will be tracked and traced with this router, but with certain issues like cryptic analysis which haven't been addressed so far. The efficiency of the router has been enhanced by introducing GMSP. At this juncture the cyber cased objects will behave randomly and rapidly which can be beyond the system capacity. At this point it is needed for implementation of certain procedures, protocols, process to handle the objects. A Framework, which is proposed will solve the problems of the factors like availability and reliability of objects and thereby will overcome the challenges like accessing of cyber cased objects in social groups effectively.

Fig. 1. The Schematic Diagram of The Onion Router

III. PROCESS AND PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

1) Accessing Of Cyber cased Objects In Social Groups:

Fig. 2. Architecture of Cyber cased object in Social Networking Groups.

The existing architecture maintains different time frames of the cyber cased objects and they are realized and retrieved from the social networking groups. Queries are written to retrieve cyber cased objects through different

database sets. This architecture could able to address positional parameters at the system level. The routers which are implemented are not much efficient to handle the nodes effectively. The routing network has not been publicized to the neighboring nodes. The existing design failed to invoke the cyber cased objects in time to facilitate the smooth process of retrieval mechanism. The existing process will take a relatively long time during invocation of cyber cased objects. The hopping procedures have not been implemented effectively. A framework GMSP is proposed to overcome the problems of availability and reliability.

2) Implementation Of GMSP Using TOR Network:

Fig. 3. Architecture of Geotagged Message Session Protocol

In the above architecture, the retrieval of the cyber cased object can be handled effectively through the protocol GMSP. This protocol will retrieve the information from the GPS by maintaining IPsec along with the public keys on individual nodes. The public keys will follow the mechanism of Kerberos where a ticketing procedure is given to key distribution centers (KDC). Public keys on the individual nodes, where the information about the cyber cased objects are shared in the network through Kerberos by implementing GMSP.

IV. CASE STUDY

A Location Based Analytics Method for Usage of Geotagged Objects in Travel Marketing Decision-Making. Analytics based on location have an important role to play in improving the travelers 'marketing system. To enhance the marketing levels over a region of demographic group, analyzing an identifying the location of different regions in a demographic group is essential. Depending on these insights making a strategic decision by travel marketing agents as far as travel package design is a difficult task. A method of location analytics to analyze the

situation has to be improvised so as to make the decision making strategy for those travel agents very much more effective. The scenario has encouraged the demographic users for implementation of a process in location analytics along with the Geo-tagged objects. This may provide a solution for agent's marketing in various ways like making decisions in an effective way to analyze the marketing travel in a better way. A design artifact is validated via a focus group and an architectural framework is defined which may apply for strategic decision support effectively.

1) *Architectural Framework:*

Fig. 4. Architectural Framework for A Location Based Analytics Methods for Usage of Geotagged objects in the Travel Marketing Decision Making

An Architectural design framework has been improvised to implement informing decisions, especially for tourism decision marketing.

2) *Evaluation of Artifact a Case Study:*

Design Science Research (DSR) will provide a visible form for all explicit considerations the marketing system with a practical approach. DSR approaches provide guidelines and rule based methodological support for development, implementation, evaluation, and adaptation of the complex systems. DSR not only provides solutions to identified organizational problems, but also provides a new dimension in designing solutions for many complex problems. Location based analytic solutions are constituted different areas with appropriate software and human interfaces by analyzing the location based systems for Geo- tagged objects through different analytical methods.

3) *Predominant Aspects of Decision making in Travel Marketing:*

Considerable issue with existing procedures to tourist behavior analysis is that outbound package designers and other travel professionals usually predetermine what should be included. This will face hassles in case of

visitors' interests are considered. At many times this will be considered in all aspects. The marketing agencies unable to form a precise notion or a picture of what activities that visitors have actually been involved in. In this regard for many tourism destinations, there is an issue of time-consuming and that made the system not really effective. The marketing agencies and marketing managers alike still face major difficulties in obtaining accurate results for following critical questions like What attract travelers when visiting a destination? What locations do travelers visit to explore these attractions? These issues have been better answered in the aspects of implementing the erstwhile architecture.

4) *Data collection and processing Techniques:*

The location analytics solution supports decision making in the perspective of both business managers and travel agencies in the tourism market. The solution artifact (architecture) aims to extract insights into tourist behavior and interests from Geo-tagged travel photos. This approach is implemented through four stages:

- i) *Travel Information Collection:* Where Geo-tagged objects processed and extracted;
- ii) *Metadata Processing:* The processing of Geo-tagged image or photo where meta-data are identified according to the interests of tourists and visited attractions at various different locations.
- iii) *Emerging Pattern Mining:* This aspect has been utilized to identify emerging attractions for different tourism markets in various levels of the tourism sector.
- iv) *Location Representative Photo:* It enhances the image processing techniques to identify popular and high quality Geo-tagged images which can be useful for developing marketing material for destinations, and developing tailored tour products. It helps the users to aim at improving the specifics of demographics as far as locating the Geo-tagged images based on analytic procedures.

5) *The Travel Information Collection:*

The Geo-tagged images with photo-sharing platforms such as Flickr (www.flickr.com). As a proxy for choosing and directly experienced locations, a user may also make use of the photo data on Flickr. This is because its reliability and capability of representation of a various data sources for capturing the traveler's interests at specific locations.

6) *Materialized Pattern Mining:*

The marketing, business managers will be interested in attracting the locations an also analyzing the differences between travel locations and Meta data. For this the data has been to be mined an in this context Emerging pattern mining (EMP) will be adopted which will really extract Geo-tagged objects without much contention. This will encourage the marketing service agents to make decision support effectively.

7) *Representation of Location Based Photo Identification :*

The travel products, and online travel websites are the major means of communication. These two will play a major role between travel agencies and travelers for location based analytics in demographic groups. This will better identify and locate specific location of the Geo-tagged images in the process of decision support for travel agents for marketing the tourism department.

Fig. 5. The visitors count to a specific location on a yearly basis.

Fig. 6. Statistical Analysis based on the visitor counts visiting different counties.

Fig.6 shows the number of visitors who visited specific locations based on their interest, and Fig. 5 depicts the visitor counts visiting to a specific location on a yearly basis have improved a lot over the year 2016. This is because the visitors could recognize and locate different locations based on positional parameters drawn during their travel. This has happened because of the statistical analysis drawn over a period of time and take travel marketing decision very effectively.

V. PROCESSING OF CYBER CASED OBJECTS

In a distributed networking environment like social networking, the cyber cased objects are linked with various different positional parameters (latitude, longitude) these parameters will continually be changing and sometimes they may be away from the system domain. In distributed systems addressing those objects need more predefined procedures to locate and identify the objects. In this case some database queries will be returned from cloud groups to retrieve and process the cyber cased objects. The existing procedures did not match to the complexities that come across the distributed network. In addition to the existing queries a protocol GMSP is introduced and it maintains IPsec and public keys on different nodes to share the information for a common purpose. The public key on the nodes will enable user to process the data without much trafficking. It can be accomplished through the protocol by

implementing TOR. The router self-assesses the location of cyber cased objects by implementing the GMSP protocol. In this way availability of cyber cased objects will be made easier and the system performance will be increased. As the percentage of availability is increasing in spite of the number of nodes in social networking group is more the performance of the cyber cased objet is increased. Percentage of availability and reliability of the cyber cased objects can be calculated based on the following equations.

$$\text{Percentage of Availability} = \frac{(\text{Number of Nodes} - \text{DownTime})}{\text{Number of Nodes}} * 100$$

$$\text{Percentage of Reliability} = (\text{Amount of DownTime} + \text{Percentage of Availability})$$

Where down time is the amount of communication time.

VI. RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

TABLE I

Down Time of nodes against availability

NUMBER OF NODES	PERCENTAGE OF AVAILABILITY	DOWN TIME
25	88	3
20	85	
15	80	
10	70	
25	80	5
20	75	
15	66.6	
10	50	

As the number of nodes for the same down- time has increased the availability has been increased for the same cyber cased object.

Fig 7. Percentage of availability with respect to number of nodes

TABLE III
Down Time of nodes against reliability

NUMBER OF NODES	PERCENTAGE OF RELIABILITY	DOWN TIME
25	91	3
20	88	
15	83	
10	73	
25	85	5
20	78	
15	71.6	
10	55	

VII. CONCLUSION

Cyber casing of objects have become very much predominant in social networking and real time systems. In a distributed networking environment like social networking, Cloud networks the issue of “availability” and “reliability” of cyber cased objects has become a major concern. In this regard a case study “Location Based Analytics” have been analyzed, realized and a solution for travel agent marketing application is provided through selection decision making as far as location statistics are concerned. This has improved the availability and reliability of the objects in a better way. The statistical analysis based on the location has resolved the issue of “availability” of cyber cased objects and facilitated the user to analyze the object’s behavior in a huge way. The statistics of the object can be in terms of GPS parameters through which the behavior can be known to the user in advance. The parameters will be realized from GPS system and thereby the availability of cyber cased object can be visualized effectively. The cyber cased object will meet the requirements of the user. It can be addressed through downtime of the object maintained through time frames of the object. The protocol GMSP maintains IPsec at each of the nodes in TOR. It will enhance the frequency of the traceability of the cyber cased and thereby improve the performance of the system.

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